

Synthesis of Mixed Ligand Complexes with Nitrido-osmium(VI) and Nitrido-osmium (VIII)

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MUCH interest has recently been shown in the chemistry of $M \equiv N$ bonded complexes of metal ions osmium¹⁻³, rhenium⁴, and molybdenum⁵. A number of mixed ligand complexes of osmium (VI) having $Os(VI) \equiv N$ group have been synthesised and characterised by elemental analysis. Presence of $Os \equiv N$ group in these compounds has been diagnosed from their spectral data in infrared region^{6,7}. Stretching frequency of the bands lies between 1020-1115 cm^{-1} depending on the nature of other ligands attached to osmium(VI) ion. Stretching frequency for $Os \equiv N$ band is given for some of the synthesised compounds in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Compound	$\nu(Os \equiv N)$ in cm^{-1}
(DipyH) $[OsNCl_4H_2O]$	1083(s)
(PhenH) $[OsNCl_4H_2O]$	1100(s)
(DipyH) $[OsNBr_4H_2O]$	1105(m)
(PhenH) $[OsNBr_4H_2O]$	1110(m)
$OsN(Oxine)_2Cl$	1110(s)
$OsNDipyBr_3$	1115(m)
$[NOsO(BigH)_2](OH)_3$	1055(m)

The compounds can be divided into two categories, one having ligand bases such as 2, 2'-dipyridyl and 1, 10-phenanthroline attached to the metal ion and the second having the protonated bases acting as cations to the complex compounds. The preparative methods have been shown schematically.

where L = 2, 2'-dipyridyl and 1, 10-phenanthroline, X = Cl, Br, and $BigH = C_2N_5H_7$.

One interesting feature of the I. R. data is, $\nu(Os \equiv N)$ of all compounds except (DipyH) $[N \equiv OsCl_4H_2O]$ and $[N \equiv Os = O(BigH)_2](OH)_3$ are very close. Very low value of $\nu(Os \equiv N)$ of $[NOs = O(BigH)_2](OH)_3$ is due to very strong donation by biguanide ligand and trans effect of $Os = O$, where the valency of Os is eight. The low value of $\nu(Os \equiv N)$ of (DipyH) $[N \equiv OsCl_4H_2O]$ is possibly due to the absence of H_2O in co-ordination sphere.

Similar compounds with rhenium(V) have been isolated. Further work is in progress for characterisation of osmium(VI) and rhenium(V) complexes.

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Organo-Cobalt(III) Complexes with Schiff Bases

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THE recent demonstration that the vitamin B₁₂ coenzyme (5'-deoxyadenosylcobalamin) contains a cobalt-carbon σ -bond^{1,2} and is a diamagnetic cobalt(III) complex containing a co-ordinated carbanion³ has stimulated research interest in the preparation and study of a wide range of organo-cobalt(III) complexes with other ligands.⁴⁻⁸ Here, in this paper, we describe the preparation and properties of some organo-cobalt(III) complexes of dibasic tetradentate Schiff bases derived by the condensation of ethylenediamine with 3-carboxysalicylaldehyde (abbreviated as BCSEN-H₄) and with orthohydroxyacetophenone (abbreviated as BHAH-H₂). This work is an extension of our previous investigations on the mixed-ligand chelates of trivalent transition metals involving Schiff bases and their organo-derivatives.⁹⁻¹⁴

Experimental :

Solvents and chemicals were purified and dried by standard methods. The electronic absorption spectra and magnetic susceptibilities were measured and elemental analysis of metal and nitrogen were performed as described previously⁹. Infrared spectra were measured and microanalysis of C, H and N were performed through commercial service of C.D.R.I., Lucknow.

Preparation of the organo-cobalt(III) complexes of bases :

(Preparations were done in N₂ atmosphere)

$[Co(BCSEN-H_2)(NH_3)_2]Cl \cdot 2H_2O$ (10 m mole) was taken in 50 ml of anhydrous THF and treated dropwise under stirring at $-20^\circ C$ with Grignard reagent (30 m mole) prepared from CH_3Br and Mg in THF. The temperature was allowed to raise under stirring and after 5 hours the reaction mixture was poured in ice-cold water and neutralised with 2N HCl.